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Evaluation of the efficiency of triacontanol hormone (TRIA) on the infestation by *Bemisia tabaci* (Aleyrodidae: Hemiptera) infested strawberry plants under greenhouses

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This study was carried out to study the effectiveness of the treatment of strawberry plants, *Fragaria ananassa* (L.), by the botanical hormone triacontanol hormone (TRIA), on the infestation by white fly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Aleyrodidae: Hemiptera), under plastic greenhouses. Experiments were carried out at two different governorates, Perkasah (Giza Governorate) and Tokh (Qaliobya Governorate) during the 2024/2025 season. Experiments were conducted on three concentrations of the successive hormone (TRIA) at both of those two locations: (15 ppm) low concentration, (30 ppm) medium concentration, and (45 ppm) high concentration. This is in addition to the fourth treatment (Control), strawberry plants that were not treated with (TRIA) before planting. The obtained results show that strawberry plants treated by a low concentration of (TRIA) (15 ppm) before planting led to lower infestation by the successive insect *B. tabaci* compared to the control (strawberry plants that were not treated by that hormone before planting). While strawberry plants treated by a medium concentration of (TRIA) (30ppm) also led to lower infestation by the successive insect *B. tabaci* compared to the control (But non-significant differences), and vice versa, strawberry plants treated by a high concentration of (TRIA) (45 ppm) led to higher infestation by that insect *B. tabaci* compared to the control.

Introduction

Strawberry plants and fruits, *Fragaria ananassa* (L.) is one of the most important vegetable plants in Egypt and around the world, which is widely cultivated both in the open fields and under greenhouses. Also, its planted areas have increased annually recently, especially in the new reclaimed lands, both for local consumption purposes and also for export to the different countries

(Gamila *et al.*, 2018). Egypt is one of the largest producers of strawberry fruits all over the world, whereas it ranks as the fifth country in the world (production and exporting of strawberry fruits), and the plantation lands with strawberry plants in Egypt were about 21573 fed. (Food and Agriculture Organization (F.A.O), 2017).

Strawberry plants were infested by many different insects, which seriously affected the total production, such as the

whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), whereas this pest is one of the seriously dangerous pests infesting strawberry plants both in the open fields and under greenhouses. Bernardi *et al.* (2013) in Brazil indicated that the insect *B. tabaci* is a very serious pest that infests strawberry plants in Brazil and causes much serious damage in both quantity and quality for the strawberry crop.

Triacontanol hormone (TRIA) is one of the more important growth regulators hormones, which play an important role for growth regulator plants, and it has an important role for improved morphological and physiological plant characteristics when used in certain concentrations (Eriksen *et al.*, 2017). Also, Srivastav and Srikant (1990) in India indicated the effectiveness of the triacontanol hormone (TRIA) on many vital processes in plants, such as photosynthesis processes, total chlorophyll, plant height and weight in some plants. Also, Kumaravelu *et al.* (2000) in India indicated that many morphological and physiological characteristics of some plants were improved when treated by certain concentrations of triacontanol hormone (TRIA).

The current study aimed to study the effectiveness of the treatment of strawberry plants, *F. ananassa*, by certain concentrations of triacontanol hormone (TRIA) before planting on the infestation by whitefly *B. tabaci* under greenhouses.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental design:

The current study was conducted on strawberry plants, *F. ananassa*, at two different locations (Governorates), Perkash (Giza Governorate) and Tokh (Qaliobyah Governorate), during season 2024/2025 under plastic greenhouses. Strawberry seedlings were planted at both locations in a timely manner for the strawberry plantation in mid of

September 2024. Experiments were conducted on 120 strawberry seedlings in each location, which were divided into four treatments (Replicates), each treatment contains 30 strawberry seedlings. The first treatment contains 30 strawberry seedlings that were immersed in a low concentration of triacontanol hormone (15 ppm) for 8 hours before planting.

The second treatment contains 30 seedlings that were immersed in a medium concentration of that hormone (30 ppm), for 8 hrs. before planting. The third treatment contains 30 seedlings that are immersed in a high concentration of hormone (45 ppm) for the same period, 8 hours before planting. Whereas the fourth treatment also contains 30 strawberry plants that were not immersed in that hormone before planting, and this treatment was carried out as a control. Strawberry seedlings were planted in plastic greenhouses at the two successive locations covered with polyethylene. Each plastic greenhouse area was divided into four parts separated by polyethylene; each part divided into five plots with an area of 5x7 m for each one. The first part contains strawberry seedlings that were not treated with the successive hormone TRIA before planting. The second part contains seedlings which treatment with a hormone (Seedlings immersed in a low concentration of hormone, 15 ppm, for 8 hrs. before planting). The third part contains seedlings that are immersed in a medium concentration of hormone, 30 ppm, for 8 hours before planting. The fourth part contains seedlings that are immersed in a high concentration of hormone, 45 ppm, for 8 hours before planting. Whereas the normal and recommended agricultural practices were conducted in a manner quite similar in both locations, and also non-chemical control for pests was conducted throughout the study period.

Then, after three weeks, when seedlings had been planted and young strawberry leaves were beginning to grow, an artificial infestation with *B. tabaci* was conducted at both locations. Strawberry leaves were collected biweekly in polyethylene bags and transported to the laboratory (PPRI) to count the number of insects.

2. Statistical analysis:

Current experiments aimed to evaluate the efficiency of three concentrations of triacontanol hormone on the infestation by *B. tabaci* infested strawberry plants. The obtained data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA), and the means were compared by L.S.D. test at 0.05 level, using the SAS program (SAS Institute, 1988).

Results and discussion

The current study aimed to study the effectiveness of the triacontanol hormone (TRIA) on the infestation by *B. tabaci* infested strawberry plants, *F. ananassa*, under greenhouses. Experiments were conducted at two locations, Perkash (Giza Governorate) and Tokh (Qalioby Governorate), during the 2014/2025 season. Experiments were conducted on three concentrations of TRIA (15ppm, 30 ppm, and 45 ppm) at both locations compared to the control.

Obtained data tabulated at Table (1) and Figures (1 and 2) show population fluctuation of *B. tabaci* infested strawberry plants at both of Giza and Qalioby Governorates during season 2024/2025. Obtained results indicated to that in Giza Governorate mean number of *B. tabaci* which infested strawberry plants did not treatment by triacontanol hormone before planting (Control) was 17.6 individual / leaf, while mean number of that insect which infested strawberry plants treatment by low concentration of TRIA (15 ppm) was 9.4 individual / leaf, whereas mean number which infested plants treatment

by medium concentration of TRIA (30 ppm) was 16.3 individual / leaf, and mean number which infested plants treatment by high concentration of TRIA (45 ppm) was 19.9 individual / leaf. That mean when treatment strawberry plants by low concentration of the successive hormone TRIA before planting the infestation by the successive insect *B. tabaci* decreased by 47% compared to control (strawberry plants did not treat by TRIA), whereas when treatment strawberry plants by medium concentration of that hormone before planting the infestation by *B. tabaci* decreased by 7.4 % (Non-significant difference) compared to control, and vice versa when treatment strawberry plants by high concentration of TRIA before planting the infestation by *B. tabaci* increased by 11.6 % compared to control. And the results were achieved at the same at Qalioby Governorate. whereas mean number of *B. tabaci* which infested strawberry plants did not treatment by triacontanol hormone before planting (Control) was 15.3 individual / leaf, while mean number of that insect which infested strawberry plants treatment by low concentration of TRIA (15 ppm) was 8.7 individual / leaf, whereas mean number which infested plants treatment by medium concentration of TRIA (15 ppm) was 14.2 individual / leaf, and mean number which infested plants treatment by high concentration of TRIA (45 ppm) was 17.0 individual / leaf. That mean when treatment strawberry plants by low concentration of TRIA before planting the infestation by the successive insect *B. tabaci* decreased by 43.2 % compared to control, whereas when treatment strawberry plants by medium concentration of TRIA before planting the infestation by *B. tabaci* decreased by 7.2 % (Non-significant difference) compared to control, and vice versa when treatment strawberry plants by

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high concentration of TRIA before increased by 17.0 % compared to planting the infestation by *B. tabaci* control.

Table (1): Population fluctuations of *Bemisia tabaci* infested strawberry plants at Giza and Qaliobya Governorates during season 2024/2025.

Date	Giza Governorate				Qaliobya Governorate			
	Control	15 ppm	30 ppm	45 ppm	Control	15 ppm	30 ppm	45 ppm
1/10/2024	9.3	5.9	8.1	11.3	7.1	4.9	6.1	8.5
8/10/2024	11.5	6.8	10.7	12.9	9.7	5.8	8.7	10.0
15/10/2024	13.7	7.5	12.8	15.8	11.8	6.5	10.8	12.3
22/10/2024	15.9	9.3	14.8	17.3	13.8	8.3	12.8	14.3
29/10/2024	16.5	10.5	15.7	18.9	14.7	9.5	13.7	15.0
5/11/2024	18.3	11.0	17.1	20.7	16.1	10.0	15.4	17.4
12/11/2024	20.7	12.3	19.5	22.8	18.5	11.3	17.5	19.7
19/11/2024	22.0	13.0	21.2	24.9	20.2	12.0	19.2	21.5
26/11/2024	24.5	14.5	23.7	26.7	22.7	13.5	21.7	23.9
3/12/2024	23.9	12.3	22.7	25.9	20.7	11.3	19.7	22.3
10/12/2024	21.7	10.5	20.8	24.5	18.8	10.5	17.8	20.7
17/12/2024	19.9	8.6	18.8	22.7	16.8	8.6	15.8	18.3
24/12/2024	18.5	7.9	17.3	20.9	15.3	7.9	14.3	17.8
31/12/2024	17.0	6.7	16.2	19.7	15.2	6.7	14.2	15.9
7/1/2025	15.5	6.0	14.7	18.9	13.7	6.0	12.7	14.2
14/1/2025	13.7	5.7	12.5	17.7	11.5	5.7	10.5	12.5
21/1/2025	11.5	5.3	10.7	15.8	9.7	5.3	8.7	10.3
28/1/2025	9.7	5.0	8.5	13.7	7.5	4.8	6.5	9.5
4/2/2025	11.6	7.8	10.3	12.0	9.3	6.8	8.3	12.0
11/2/2025	13.9	8.3	12.7	15.9	11.7	7.3	10.7	13.9
18/2/2025	15.7	9.0	13.9	17.7	12.9	8.0	11.9	16.5
25/2/2025	16.9	9.5	15.7	18.2	13.7	8.5	12.7	17.0
4/3/2025	18.3	10.0	16.5	20.8	14.5	9.0	13.5	19.1
11/3/2025	20.7	11.2	18.5	22.7	26.5	10.2	22.5	21.4
18/3/2025	22.5	12.3	20.7	24.5	18.7	11.3	17.7	23.7
25/3/2025	24.7	13.0	22.5	26.9	20.5	12.0	19.5	25.0
1/4/2025	25.8	14.2	23.5	27.5	21.5	13.2	20.5	26.3
Total	473.9	254.1	440.1	537.3	413.1	234.9	383.4	459.0
Mean	17.6	9.4	16.3	19.9	15.3	8.7	14.2	17.0
Reduction %	-	(-) 47.0	(-) 7.4	(+) 11.6	-	(-) 43.2	(-) 7.2	(+) 10.0
F_(0.05)	427.73				385.97			
L. S. D.	1.075				1.035			

Means within columns bearing different subscripts are significantly different (P < 0.05).

Figure (1): Population mean number of *Bemisia tabaci* infested strawberry plants at Giza Governorate during season 2024/2025.

Figure (2): Population mean number of *Bemisia tabaci* infested strawberry plants at Qaliobya Governorate during season 2024/2025.

Statistical analysis showed that there were significant differences between the mean numbers of the successive insect *B. tabaci* infested strawberry plants that were treated by low and high concentrations of TRIA compared to the control, whereas there were no significant differences between the mean numbers of the successive insect *B. tabaci* infested strawberry plants that were treated by medium concentrations of TRIA compared to the control. These results were similar at both of the two successive locations (Governorates).

Heba (2013) in Egypt indicated that *Zea mays* plants treated with a low concentration of triacontanol hormone (35 ppm) had a low infestation of *Euprepocnemis plorans* compared to the control, and the plants treated with a high concentration of that hormone TRIA (50 ppm) led to a high infestation of that insect compared to the control.

Effect of triacontanol hormone on the morphological and physiological adjectives of strawberry plants:

Data tabulated at Table (2) and Figures (3,4, and 5) show the effectiveness of treatment strawberry plants *F. ananassa* by triacontanol hormone (TRIA) before planting on the important morphological adjectives (Root length, shoot length and plant height) and also important internal substances secreted by these plants (total sugars, carbohydrates, total proteins, amino acids and total phenols).

Obtained results indicated that when strawberry plants were treated with a low concentration of the triacontanol hormone (15 ppm), it led to improved morphological adjectives of strawberry plants and also important internal substances secreted by these plants compared to the control (strawberry plants not treated by TRIA). When strawberry plants were treated with a medium concentration of that hormone (30 ppm), it also led to improved morphological and physiological adjectives of strawberry plants compared to the control (But it had non-significant differences).

Table (2): Effectiveness of triacontanol hormone on the morphological and physiological adjectives of strawberry plants.

Adjective	Control	15 ppm	30 ppm	45 ppm	F (0.05)	L. S. D.
Root height (cm)	17.3 ^a	22.5 ^c	18.9 ^a	15.7 ^b	322.12	1.025
Shoot height (cm)	60.7 ^a	75.2 ^c	65.5 ^a	54.3 ^b	346.87	1.076
Plant height (cm)	78.0 ^a	97.7 ^c	84.4 ^a	70.0 ^b	289.66	1.044
Total sugars (mg/100g)	30.7 ^a	39.5 ^c	33.7 ^a	27.3 ^b	411.23	1.089
Carbohydrates (mg/100g)	10.7 ^a	14.5 ^c	12.0 ^a	9.0 ^b	351.22	1.034
Total proteins (mg/100g)	3.7 ^a	5.7 ^c	4.3 ^a	3.0 ^b	344.82	1.075
Amino acids (mg/100g)	4.5 ^a	6.3 ^c	5.2 ^a	3.7 ^b	298.55	1.037
Total phenols (mg/100g)	9.8 ^a	12.5 ^c	10.3 ^a	8.5 ^b	425.12	1.082

Means within columns bearing different subscripts are significantly different (P < 0.05).

Figure (3): Effectiveness of triacontanol hormone on the morphological and adjectives of strawberry plants.

Figure (4): Effectiveness of triacontanol hormone on the physiological adjectives of strawberry plants.

Figure (5): Effectiveness of triacontanol hormone on the physiological adjectives of strawberry plants.

Lastly, treating strawberry plants with a high concentration of TRIA (45 ppm) led to negative effects on morphological and physiological adjectives of strawberry plants compared to the control. Eriksen *et al.* (2017) in Oslo (Norway) indicated that when treating tomato and maize plants with triacontanol hormone, it led to positive effects on these plants, stimulated a significant increase in the fresh and dry weight of the tomato plants, and also on leaf area. TRIA plays an important role at different stages of development.

Shukla *et al.* (2022) in the Netherlands referred to the effectiveness of triacontanol (TRIA) at lower concentrations on photosynthesis, growth, and plant hormones of tested plants, but these vital processes decreased when treated plants were exposed to higher concentrations of that hormone. Gupta

et al. (2021) in India indicated that important morphological and physiological characteristics of the successive plants were improved when they treated these plants with certain concentrations of (TRIA). The current study aimed to study the effectiveness of treating strawberry plants, *F. ananassa*, with three concentrations of the botanical hormone triacontanol hormone TRIA on the infestation by whitefly *B. tabaci*. Results obtained indicated to that strawberry plants treatment by low concentration of TRIA (15 ppm) led to decreasing population number of *B. tabaci*, and also improved morphological and physiological adjectives of strawberry plants, while strawberry plants treatment by medium concentration of TRIA (30 ppm) also led to decreasing population number of *B. tabaci*, and improving morphological and

physiological adjectives of strawberry plants (But did not significantly differences), whereas treatment by high concentration of TRIA (45 ppm) led to increasing population number of *B. tabaci* and negative effectiveness on morphological and physiological adjectives of strawberry plants compared to control. So, we can recommend using this hormone in low concentration (15 ppm) in Integrated Pest Management Programs (I.P.M.) for controlling *B. tabaci* infesting strawberry plants.

References

- Bernardi, D.; Araujo, E.; Botton, M. and Mogor, A. (2013):** *Bemisia tabaci* population dynamics associated with strawberry. Neotropical Entomology, 43(5): 630- 635.
- Eriksen, A.; Sellden, G.; Skogen, D. and Nilsen, S. (2017):** Comparative analyses of the effect of triacontanol hormone on photosynthesis, photorespiration and growth of tomato (C3-plant) and maize (C 4-plant). Planta, 152 (1): 44-49. doi:10.1007/BF0 0384983.
- Food and Agriculture Organization (F.A.O) (2017):** FAO stresses the importance of innovative approaches during meeting of the committee on World Food Security, 6(3): 25-27.
- Gamila, H.; Ghada, M. and Saneya, R. (2018):** Seasonal fluctuation of main pests inhabiting strawberry plants in relation to certain weather factors at Sharkia Governorate, Egypt. Middle East Journal, 7(2): 481- 491.
- Gupta, G.; Yadav, S. R. and Bhattacharya, A. K. (2009):** Influence of synthetic plant growth substances on the survivorship and developmental parameters of *Spilarctia obliqua* Walker (Lepidoptera: Arctiidae). Journal of Pest Science, 82(1):41-46. doi:10.1007/s10340-008-0217-x
- Heba, M. H. (2013):** The potential role of triacontanol in certain physiological aspects of *Zea mays* L. single cross Giza 310 grown under normal and environmental stress conditions. Ph.D. Thesis, Fac. of Science, Ain Shams University.225pp.
- Knowles NR, Ries SK. (1981):** Rapid growth and apparent total nitrogen increase in rice and corn plants following applications of Triacontanol. Plant Physiology, 68(6):1279-1284. doi:10.1104/pp.68.6.1279.
- Kumaravelu, G.; David, V.D. and Ramanujam, M. (2000):** Triacontanol- induced changes in the growth, photosynthetic pigments, cell metabolites, flowering and yield of green gram. Biologia Plantarum, 43: 287-290. https://doi.org/10.1023/A: 1002724831619
- McKee, G.J.; Goodhue, R.E.; Zalom, F.G. Carter, C.A. and Chalfant, J.A. (2009):** Population dynamics and the economics of invasive species management: The greenhouse whitefly in California-grown strawberries. Journal of Environmental Management, 90(1): 561-570. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman. 2007.12.011
- SAS Institute (1988):** SAS-STAT User's Guide, Ver.6.03.SAS Institute Inc., Cary, North Carolina.

Shukla, A., Abad Farooqi, A.H., Shukla, Y.N. and Sharma, F. (1992): Effect of triacontanol and chlormequat on growth, plant hormones and artemisinin yield in *Artemisia annua* L. *Plant Growth Regulation*, 11(5):165–171. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00024071>.

Srivastav, N.K. and Srikant S. (1990): Effect of triacontanol on photosynthesis, alkaloid content and growth in opium poppy (*Papaver Somniferum* L.). *Plant Growth Regulation*, 9: 65-71. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00025280>.